

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE OLD ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation. Old English, which covered the 5th-12th centuries, was a language rich in numerous morphological features inherited from the Proto-Germanic language. The grammatical structure of Old English, which was not so rich in terms of vocabulary, was as difficult as modern German. The use of a large number of case, gender, and quantitative suffixes in the language, as well as the existence of strict grammatical coordination between words within a sentence, was a characteristic feature of Old English, which fundamentally distinguished it from the English of the Middle and Modern periods. By the Middle Ages, Old English had begun to be renewed at all levels of the language under the influence of other foreign languages and to become a completely new structured analytical language. Throughout its evolution, English has always undergone fundamental changes under the influence of foreign languages. The article focuses on the issues mentioned and interprets them from a diachronic perspective.

Keywords: *Proto-Germanic language, grammatical concord, synthetic language, analytical language, syncretism*

Annotatsiya. 5–12-asrlarni qamrab olgan qadimgi ingliz tili buyuk german tilidan meros bo‘lib qolgan ko‘plab morfologik belgilarga boy til edi. So‘z boyligi jihatidan unchalik boy bo‘lmagan qadimgi ingliz tilining grammatik tuzilishi hozirgi nemis tilidagidek qiyin edi. Tilda ko‘p sonli hol, jins va miqdoriy qo‘shimchalarning qo‘llanilishi, shuningdek, gap ichidagi so‘zlar o‘rtasida qat’iy grammatik muvofiqlikning mavjudligi qadimgi ingliz tilining o‘ziga xos xususiyati bo‘lib, uni o‘rta va yangi davr ingliz tilidan tubdan ajratib turdi. O‘rta asrlarga kelib eski ingliz tili boshqa xorijiy tillar ta’sirida tilning barcha darajalarida yangilana boshladi va butunlay yangi tuzilgan analitik tilga aylana boshladi. Ingliz tili o‘zining butun evolyutsiyasi davomida chet tillari ta’sirida doimo tub o‘zgarishlarga duch keldi. Maqolada ko‘rsatilgan masalalarga e’tibor qaratilgan va ular diaxronik nuqtai nazardan izohlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *protogerman tili, grammatik kelishik, sintetik til, analitik til, sinkretizm*

English, which is used in our time as a means of global communication with its unique linguistic qualities across a wide geographical area, was a poorly developed tribal language brought to the islands by the Anglo, Saxon, and Jute tribes who invaded the British Isles in the 5th century and spoken in various dialects of the same language. *“The Germanic dialects spoken in the Anglo-Saxon kingdoms were distinct but mutually intelligible varieties that began to evolve from the tribal tongues spoken by the settlers’ continental ancestors. The varieties can be grouped into four main types – Northumbrian, Kentish, Mercian and West Saxon. We refer to these dialects together as Old English”* [4, p.4]. During this period, Latin was widely used in the islands as a language of instruction and promotion of religious and secular knowledge, as the spread of Christianity in the islands had strengthened Latin's position as the language of church and state in these lands. Anglo-Saxon English was subject to centuries of Latin influence, and changes began to occur in the language. In particular, English borrowed a significant number of words from Latin in terms of vocabulary.

Despite its changes over time, the language spoken by the Anglo-Saxon tribes who came from the Scandinavian Peninsula to claim new lands on the European continent is a Germanic language and contains features inherited from the Great Germanic language. This language was spoken in the southwestern part of what is now England and Scotland from the mid-5th century to the mid-12th century. Among these features, the phonetic, grammatical, and lexical system of the language are particularly noteworthy.

In the later stages of its evolution, the English language underwent radical changes at all levels, to the point that even modern native speakers cannot read or understand anything in Old English without special training. Studies show that Old English has undergone 85% of changes since the Modern era, leaving very little of this language intact [2].

Old English was fundamentally different from medieval and modern English at all levels of the language hierarchy. As such, Old English was a synthetic language with suffixes and had a complex grammatical structure. This language did not resemble modern English in terms of pronunciation and writing. Old English used the runic alphabet brought to the islands by Scandinavian tribes until the Latin alphabet was introduced in the 12th century.

The runic alphabet slowed down the development of writing, because it was difficult to write with this alphabet. Starting from the 12th century, an alphabet based on the Latin script was used. *“The Anglo-Saxons also used the alphabet we use now. However, their alphabet did not have signs to indicate the letters j, v, k, q, x, z, w. The letters æ, þ, ð that they used are not used in spelling today”* [3, p.4].

In Old English, the letter combination *th* was represented by the letter *ð*, and *w* by the letter *ƿ(wynn)*. In Old English, long and short vowels – *a, æ, i, o, u, y*; two diphthongs – *ea, eo* were used. The letter *y* – was sometimes written as *ie*. A line called a macron was written above long vowels as a sign of length, for example, as in the words *stān – stone, rāp – rope, bāt – boat*.

In Old English, nouns, verbs, and pronouns were a synthetic language with a complex grammatical system, morphological features, and rich in homonym suffixes indicating case, person, tense, and grammatical gender, creating syncretism. The vocabulary of Old English was originally composed of words of Germanic origin. However, as the language was influenced, these words left the language and English was enriched with words borrowed from other languages. However, even today, English still uses some words from Old English. For example, words such as *mann* (*man*), *wīf* (*wife, woman*), *cild* (*child*), *hūs* (*house*), *mete* (*meat, food*), *gærs* (*grass*), *lēaf* (*leaf*), *gōd* (*good*), *strang* (*strong*), *etan* (*eat*), *drincan* (*drink*), *weall* (*wall*), *heah* (*high*) [1, p.1] have undergone certain changes and are now widely used in the language as words of original English ones. Diachronic studies prove that Old English, which was a synthetic language, tended towards analyticity throughout its evolution and is currently being studied as an analytic language.

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BADIIY MATNNING LUG‘AVIY-USLUBIY XUSUSIYATLARI (Odil Yoqubov asarlari misolida)

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada til va tafakkurning o‘zaro munosabati, bu aloqadorlikning badiiy asar nutqida ifoda etilishi, unda til birliklarining aktuallashuviga sabab tug‘diruvchi omillar to‘g‘risida so‘z yuritiladi. Odil Yoqubovning “Ulug‘bek xazinasi”, “Diyonat” nomli asarlari misolida badiiy matnning lug‘aviy-uslubiy xususiyatlari tahlil etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: til, tafakkur, ularning o‘zaro munosabati, badiiy asar tili ijodiy tafakkurning namoyon bo‘lish shakllaridan biri sifatida, lug‘aviy-uslubiy xususiyatlarning lingvopoetik tahlili.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается взаимосвязь языка и мышления, выражение этой взаимосвязи в речи художественного произведения и факторы, обуславливающие актуализацию языковых единиц в нём. Лексико-стилистические особенности художественного текста анализируются на примере произведений Одила Якубова «Сокровище Улугбека» и «Дийонат»

Ключевые слова: язык, мышление, их взаимосвязь, язык художественного произведения как одна из форм проявления творческой мысли, лингвопоэтический анализ лексико-стилистических особенностей.